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Temporal Variations in Physico-Chemical Properties of Water in Coringa Mangrove Estuary Near Coringa Village, East Godavari District, Andhra Pradesh, India.

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Abstract: The living organisms are greatly influenced by the abiotic factors in an aquatic ecosystem. The biodiversity and population size of each species in aquatic ecosystem is determined by the water quality. The physico-chemical properties of water in Coringa mangroves area, East Godavari District, Andhra Pradesh, India were monitored for one year. Monthly changes in physical and chemical properties of water such as temperature, pH, dissolved oxygen, free carbon dioxide, alkalinity, hardness and salinity were analyzed for a period of one year from 12th July 2012 to 12th June 2013. All the studied parameters found that the results of water quality are within the permissible limits to support aquatic life.

Keywords: *Coringa mangroves area, Physico-chemical parameters, Monthly variation*

INTRODUCTION

Water is one of the most important components of the ecosystem. Better quality of water is described by its physical, chemical and biological characteristics. These parameters are correlated with one another and the significant one would be useful to indicate the quality of water. Due to increased human population, industrialization, use of fertilizers in agriculture and man-made activity, the natural aquatic resources are affected by heavy and varied pollution leading to poor water quality and depletion of aquatic organisms. It is therefore necessary to check the quality of water periodically to monitor the level of contamination if any in the water. To understand the biological phenomena fully,

knowledge of chemistry of water is essential which reveals much information about the metabolism of the ecosystem and explain the general hydro-biological relationship.

River water contains a large number of dissolved compounds of varying magnitude¹. Parmar *et al.*² studied the pollution level and water quality indexing of main rivers of Punjab. Indian environment is found to be very dynamic especially with respect to temperature and rainfall³. The regional climatic models would not be able to predict local climate, because average quantities of precipitation during the south-west monsoon is affected by temperature and pressure variability during preceding winter⁴. Simultaneous effect of water pollution and eutrophication on the concentration of dissolved oxygen was studied in a water body⁵. The Physico-chemical properties of water and the dependence of all life processes on these factors make it desirable to take as an environment. The present study deals with the analysis of Physico-chemical parameters of water in Coringa mangroves area, East Godavari district, AP. In India till now several researchers have done work on physico-chemical and biological characteristics of standing and running water resources⁶.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The water samples from mangrove areas were collected every month in plastic bottles from three different stations in the morning hours between 9 to 11 AM. After recording the temperature and pH of the water onsite, the water samples were immediately brought to the laboratory and the remaining physico-chemical properties; salinity, alkalinity, hardness, dissolved oxygen and free carbon dioxide were analyzed following standard methods. The temperature of surface water onsite at various locations was measured using standard mercury thermometer. The pH of water onsite was measured using microprocessor based pocket pH meter (Hanna Pocket pH Meter). Dissolved oxygen in the water samples which were collected in BOD bottles was estimated following modified Winkler's method⁷. Salinity of water samples was estimated by the Mohr-Knudsen method⁸. Alkalinity and Hardness were determined by titration method using EDTA solution⁹ and CO₂ was estimated by titration method using NaOH¹⁰.

Study Area: The study area is located in the Godavari river zone towards southern side of the Kakinada Bay (82°12' - 82°21' East and 16°31' - 16°54' North) which has dense mangrove vegetation and extensive mudflats and the area is basically used for domestic, agriculture purposes and fisheries activity¹¹.

Fig 1: Google satellite map of the Coringa Mangroves area representing study area and sampling location (Courtesy: Google Earth)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The seasonal variations in water quality with respect to temperature, pH, salinity, alkalinity, hardness, dissolved oxygen and carbon dioxide in the studied mangrove area was analyzed every month for a period of one year during July 2012 to June 2013 and the results are presented in the table.

Table 1: Month-wise water quality analyses in the study area during July 2012 and June 2013.

	Temperature (°C)	pH	Salinity (mg/L)	Alkalinity (mg/L)	Hardness (mg/L)	Dissolved Oxygen (mg/L)	Carbon Dioxide (mg/L)
July	28	8	1	146	130	4.6	1.65
August	32	7.68	0	120	120	4.8	1.89
September	31	8	0.24	80	145	5.6	0.99
October	32	7.68	0	120	120	4.8	1.89
November	32	7.2	0.2	120	290	6.5	3.5
December	30	7.2	2.3	112	280	2	3.5
January	33	7.4	1.04	82	240	3.8	0.99
February	34	8	1	85	300	7	0.99
March	30	8	0.3	100	296	6.4	1.99
April	30	8	0.2	110	285	7.3	1.5
May	34	8.2	0.5	112	290	7	0.99
June	29	8	0.2	120	130	6.4	0.99

Water Temperature: In the present study water temperature ranges from 28°C to 34°C. The maximum temperature of 34°C was recorded in the month of February and May (Cool & Summer months) and minimum temperature of 28°C in the month of July (Rainy season). It showed that higher temperature was recorded in summer and relatively low in rainy season. In this study we observed that during summer, water temperature was high due to low water level and higher atmospheric temperature. Atmospheric temperature is an important factor which influences the chemical, biochemical and biological characteristics of water body.

Fig 2: Seasonal variations in the water temperature in Coringa mangrove estuary.

pH: The pH values of water in Coringa mangrove estuarine area ranges from 7.2 to 8.5 during various seasons of a year. The maximum pH value (8.5) was recorded in the month of May (summer) and minimum (7.2) in the month of November and December (winter). The factors such as air temperature, water salinity, alkalinity etc. bring about changes in the pH of water.

Most of the bio-chemical and chemical reactions are influenced by pH. The reduced rate of photosynthetic activities leads to reduction in the assimilation of carbon dioxide and bicarbonates which is ultimately responsible for increase in temperature during the summer month¹².

Fig 3: Seasonal variations in the pH of water in Coringa mangrove estuary

Salinity: The Salinity of mangrove estuarine water during various seasons ranges from 0.0 mg/L to 2.3 mg/L. The maximum salinity of water (2.3 mg/L) was recorded in the month of December (winter) and minimum salinity (0.0 mg/L) in August and October months. During the month of December, because of low rain fall and high tides salinity was recorded high at the time of sample collection. And during the month of August and October because of rains and low tides salinity was high.

Fig 4: Water salinity variations in Coringa mangrove estuary during various seasons.

Alkalinity: Seasonal variations in water alkalinity in Coringa mangrove area range from 146.0 mg/L to 80.0 mg/L. The maximum value (146.0 mg/L) was recorded in the month of July (rainy season) and minimum value was (80.0 mg/L) was recorded in the month of September. The maximum value of alkalinity in the month of July is attributed to increased bicarbonates in the water that were brought by floods. Here also similar values are reported that maximum in rainy season due to high photosynthetic rate¹³.

Fig 5: Seasonal variations in water Alkalinity in Coringa mangrove estuary.

Hardness: The hardness of water in the studied mangrove area fluctuates from 120 mg/L to 300 mg/L during various seasons. The maximum value (300 mg/L) was recorded in the month of February and minimum value was (120 mg/L) in the month of August and October.

Fig 6: Seasonal variations in water Hardness in Coringa mangrove estuary.

Dissolved Oxygen (Do): The amount of dissolved oxygen (DO) fluctuates during various seasons between 2 mg/L and 7.3 mg/L. The maximum amount of DO (7.3 mg/L) was recorded in the month of April and minimum amount (2 mg/L) in the month of December. The high amount of DO in summer is due to increased duration of bright sunlight. It can influence the percentage of soluble gases.

The increased duration and intensity of sunlight during summer seems to accelerate photosynthetic activity of phytoplankton, which utilize CO₂ and release oxygen. This possibly accounts for the greater quantities of O₂ recorded during summer. The quantity of DO is lowest during winter.

Fig 7: Seasonal variation of dissolved oxygen in the water of Coringa mangrove estuary.

Free Carbon Dioxide: The levels of free CO₂ in the Coringa mangrove water ranges from 0.99 mg/L to 3.5 mg/L during various seasons. The highest levels CO₂ (3.5 mg/L) were recorded in November and December months and low CO₂ levels (0.99 mg/L) in the months of September, January, February, May and June.

Fig 8: Seasonal variations in the levels of Carbon dioxide in the water of Coringa mangrove area.

CONCLUSION

The seasonal variations in water quality with respect to temperature, pH, salinity, alkalinity, hardness, dissolved oxygen and carbon dioxide in the studied mangrove area was analyzed every month for a period of one year during July 2012 to June 2013. All the studied parameters found that the results of water quality are within the permissible limits to support aquatic life.

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